

“Matter and Antimatter: Twins or Siamese?”

Their Eternal Oscillation in Time and Quantum Entanglement in the Creation of the Universe”

A theoretical approach to the structure and motion of matter as a result of the dynamic interaction of matter and antimatter

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To my brother **Antonis Ventouris**,
with whom I journeyed,
and who now awaits me in the light,

and to my grandson **Nysis Margaris**,
who carries the journey into the future.

Abstract

This essay proposes a new theoretical approach to the fundamental structure of matter, focusing on the dynamic and complementary relationship between matter and antimatter. According to the model developed, matter is not a single, autonomous system, but arises from a continuous interaction of two symmetric space-time systems — matter and antimatter — in a permanent and inseparable relationship of coexistence.

The proposal extends the quantum property of energy to the entire spectrum of the structure of matter as a result of the symmetrical and complementary cooperation of the two space-time systems. Matter and antimatter were born together to build worlds.

This new view of the structure of Matter, the fundamental coexistence and alternation of the two space-time systems of matter-antimatter, creates new parameters and hypotheses to be investigated. The addition of negative time is a parameter that can add new fields to the research. In this context, our proposal for investigating the possibility that the magnetic field is a manifestation and result of the reversal and oscillation of the system in time is also placed as it gives a possible explanation for the property of the spin of particles as "angular momentum in time".

Of particular importance is that this proposal meets the relativistic equations of quantum mechanics, Klein–Gordon and Dirac, offering a century later a coherent interpretation of their findings.

This proposal is applied to the interpretation of light as a structure that embodies the balanced coexistence of an e^-e^+ pair, providing a physical explanation for the quantization of energy and the main interactions of light with matter. Furthermore, it is shown how this coexistence eliminates theoretical difficulties such as the infinities that arise in quantum electrodynamics.

While this work does not present formal mathematical proofs, it aims to contribute to the conceptual and philosophical foundations of modern physics by suggesting an alternative perspective on the relation between light, matter, and antimatter. It is a faint, whispered voice of Antimatter, claiming its existence and survival in our world.

Note: This essay is also available in Greek: [Ventouri_Matter-Antimatter2025_GR.pdf](#)

Σημείωση: Αυτό το δοκίμιο είναι επίσης διαθέσιμο στα ελληνικά: [Ventouri_Matter-Antimatter2025_GR.pdf](#)

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Introduction – Prologue

Physics teaches us that in the Big Bang at the dawn of the Universe, matter prevailed over antimatter. According to the inflationary model, matter and antimatter annihilated each other, except for a small excess of matter that remained and gave rise to the universe we know. This is how the absence of antimatter from our perceived cosmos is theoretically explained.

Established physics regards the disappearance of antimatter as one of the great enigmas of cosmology. Within the dominant model, matter is thought to have slightly prevailed in the initial symmetry, leading to our Universe. Antimatter is treated as an exotic copy of matter — its spatiotemporal opposite, hostile and antagonistic. Its rare appearances in our visible universe are produced only under exceptional conditions and immediately vanish through mutual annihilation with matter.

In the present model, this view is overturned. Antimatter has not vanished from the Universe; it is intertwined with matter in a Siamese relationship: symmetrical, dynamic, and functionally creative.

The matter we perceive is not an autonomous structure. It emerges from an inner balance between two fundamental forms — two distinct spatiotemporal systems: matter and antimatter in an indivisible bond. This fundamental duality — revealed, as we will see, in the very structure of the photon, the carrier of energy — is not confined to photons and radiation alone, but extends across the entire spectrum of physical reality.

Antimatter never disappeared from the Universe.

It was not destroyed, but evolved and transformed, bound into structures where coexistence, cooperation, and complementarity — rather than annihilation — constitute the fundamental law. Matter and antimatter were born together, opposite yet complementary, so that they might build worlds.

This conclusion arises naturally and self-evidently from the very structure of matter as recorded by the Standard Model, in which the building blocks of atomic nuclei, mesons, bosons, and all particles of matter (quarks–antiquarks, gluons, all mesons, bosons, and interacting particles at every scale) consist of equal amounts of matter and antimatter in symmetrical structures without immediate annihilation.

In the Standard Model, matter is described as a set of elementary particles with properties such as mass, charge, and spin. Yet antimatter participates equally and symmetrically in their structure — a fact noted in particle tables but never meaningfully interpreted. Although its presence and complementary role within matter is systematic, no one seems to ask where all this antimatter originates, why it appears in equal quantities with matter within elementary particles, and what its role truly is. Its traces are therefore sought in vain with telescopes across

the distant universe, while models such as cosmic inflation are invoked to account for its supposed absence.

Immediately after the Big Bang, matter existed in the form of a quark–gluon plasma (QGP), a nearly perfect liquid with minimal viscosity: a seething plasma of quarks of all colors and gluons¹ — the most elementary particles of matter and antimatter — from which protons and neutrons would later be formed. This is confirmed by experiments merging gold nuclei at 99.95% the speed of light at the Relativistic Heavy Ion Collider (RHIC) of Brookhaven National Laboratory in New York, which produce temperatures above a trillion degrees, a hundred thousand times that of the Sun.

Theory predicts that this state must have prevailed for about 10 μ sec after the Big Bang, before the formation of known matter. To understand the creation of the universe, one must understand the formation of the quark–gluon “soup” and, after the first three minutes, the birth of ordinary atomic nuclei. (The first atoms appeared about 400,000 years later.)

An amniotic fluid of matter and antimatter particles was the primordial substance. Within this womb, bisubstantial Matter was conceived; from this womb it emerged — the Matter that we are.

The two spatiotemporal states of matter and antimatter thus form a Siamese mechanism, with powerful energetic structures spanning the entire spectrum of physical reality. Our Matter is but a derivative of these two primordial entities, matter and antimatter, born together and working together to build worlds..

This work does not claim to stand against the Standard Model of Physics, nor to compete with the foundations of established scientific knowledge. Instead, it stands with respect and builds upon its accepted principles and findings, while proposing an alternative interpretation inspired by the very fascination of the questions the Standard Model leaves open. It is a theoretical approach intended to enrich the dialogue, not to cancel it.

1. The Dual Nature of Matter

The concept of duality applies not only to the photon—understood here as an internal relation between matter and antimatter—but also to all matter particles as described by the Standard Model. This calls for a new framework for understanding energy, motion, and interactions. The

¹ *According to Quantum Chromodynamics, quarks carry three colors (red, green, blue), while antiquarks carry the corresponding anticolors. The carriers of the strong interaction are the gluons, which are composed of color–anticolor combinations. There are eight independent such combinations, corresponding to the 8 gluons. Gluons interact both with quarks and with each other, creating a complex dynamics that gives rise to a “sea” of quarks, antiquarks, and gluons inside protons and neutrons.*

model proposed here is grounded in the established laws and principles of physics, but seeks to weave them into a broader picture of Nature that interprets and unifies them coherently.

The coexistence of matter and antimatter within all elementary particles and within the atoms that form Matter leads to the idea of a fundamental dual nature. Matter and antimatter are treated as two separate space–time systems, with mirrored spatial and temporal dimensions, obeying CPT symmetry. Together they form the “Siamese trunk” of the matter we know, two faces looking in opposite directions of space–time, alternating in their orientation.

This dual system is necessarily quantized: as it oscillates between the two space–time states, it generates the full spectrum of electromagnetic frequencies. Consequently, all motion and manifestations of matter are quantized, since the reversible time of CPT symmetry ($-t \leftrightarrow +t$) is involved at every scale, from the subatomic to the cosmic.

According to the uncertainty principle, any act of “measurement” disturbs the system under observation. In this model, each measurement corresponds to an oscillation: the system passes from state K1 to K2, from K2 to K3, and so forth. Motion itself arises from this chain of state transitions. More generally, matter and antimatter form a quantum system in which every oscillation-measurement transforms the state ($Ka/Ma \rightarrow Ka/Mva$). The continuous sequence of oscillations and measurements produces displacement—movement—in space and time.

Thus, motion is the direct result of disturbance through measurement, and the flow of time is granular, determined by the oscillation frequency between negative time ($-t$) and positive time ($+t$). To observation, however, both time and motion appear continuous.

We are therefore dealing with two interwoven space–time systems of matter and antimatter. Their perpetual alternation constitutes the underlying mechanism of the structure and dynamics of Matter as a whole. In this sense, Matter itself is **a quantum object** in which space and time emerge in quantized form, oscillating between positive and negative regimes. This oscillation shapes the structure, the energy background, and the forces that sustain Matter.

Perhaps this very mechanism—the oscillation between two space–time systems—can explain the origin of mass. If an **excitatory oscillator** enforces resonance between the oscillation frequencies of structured matter, then mass arises not from an inertial field intrinsic to a point particle, but from the oscillatory mechanism itself. Mass, in this view, is a manifestation of the quantum process of duality.

In summary, the two space–time systems together form a closed energy system, a neutral circuit. As a whole it is indifferent to the external universe, just as dark matter appears indifferent to us. Our world, in this perspective, may be invisible to other possible universes.

In each system separately, matter corresponds to positive space (χ, ψ, ζ) combined with positive time ($+t$), while antimatter corresponds to negative space ($-\chi, -\psi, -\zeta$) combined with negative time ($-t$). Taken together, matter and antimatter form an energetically neutral “egg,”

a closed circuit that interacts only with itself and with systems of the same nature. At their core, these are simply frequencies—energy fields—that diffuse throughout the universe, detectable only by decoders of the same kind.

It is possible that the primordial “soup” also produced other forms of Matter—different systems—yet all must consist of two inverse, complementary space–time components forming a quantum dipole. Only in this way can energy, structure, and Matter emerge.

This perspective suggests the existence of multiple, superimposed universes, each with its own space–time system of matter, mutually indifferent, coexisting in a “**non-space.**” Each system generates its own space and laws, but remains imperceptible to other systems with different spectra of frequencies and interactions.

Our own system may in fact involve more dimensions than the four usually considered. As it oscillates between two space–times, a fifth dimension naturally appears, with negative time (–t) participating fully. Moreover, there may be an additional dimension: the horizon of interaction between matter and antimatter. This horizon would be the true body of our Siamese Matter, the arena where duality shapes the universe we inhabit.

2. Time as a Bipolar Oscillation Mechanism

Within the framework of matter–antimatter coexistence, time does not appear as a neutral background on which events unfold, but as a direct consequence of their oscillation. If matter and antimatter are two complementary space–time systems, then their continuous alternation — their oscillation — not only builds the structure of energy and motion, but also generates the very fabric of time.

Here, time is not a uniform flow but the outcome of a bipolar mechanism: the oscillation between negative and positive time in the two space–time systems of matter and antimatter. The two components oscillate inversely in time. This fundamental property explains why all the particles that constitute matter — mesons, bosons, atomic nuclei, as well as the interaction particles of the strong, weak, and electromagnetic forces — can incorporate both matter and antimatter without annihilating. Without this property, the creation of Matter would be impossible, as opposite particles would mutually eliminate each other before forming any structure.

The inversion in time guarantees the coexistence and stability of particles and antiparticles within every composite particle. Although they coexist in a bound state, they do not move within the same time. Schematically, when the matter particle is at one end of the oscillation of a pendulum swinging in time, the corresponding antiparticle is at the opposite end. It is impossible for them to meet, since such a meeting would mean the coincidence of their past with their future — a moment that cannot exist.

The transition from one state to the other constitutes the elementary “pulse” of time. Thus, time appears quantized: a granular sequence of transitions between $-t$ and $+t$, which, through their continuous alternation, are perceived as a smooth and uninterrupted flow.

The mechanism of dipole oscillation in time offers a possible explanation for the origin of the magnetic field as a manifestation of the continuous temporal oscillation from $+t$ to $-t$ and vice versa and is probably linked to the spin of the particles. The property of the spin of particles is thus interpreted as angular momentum in time and not in space and this property is considered a basic factor in the creation of the magnetic field.

From this perspective, two main representations can be considered:

First representation: the two systems evolve independently and remain correlated through non-local updating (analogous to quantum entanglement).

Second representation: the two systems advance step by step in a common oscillation. This version preserves the unity of matter and also offers a possible explanation for the origin of the magnetic field as a manifestation of temporal oscillation (see also Section 4a).

Both representations are depicted in the figures that follow.

A First case:

Figure 6. (in Greek): two independent space–time systems of matter and antimatter, synchronized through continuous non-local updating (entanglement).

Labels (translation):

- ενημέρωση → *updating*
- χωροχρόνος ύλης – χωροχρόνος αντιύλης → *space-time of matter – space-time of antimatter*
- ο χρόνος είναι συνεχής και αθροιστικός, τα βελη του χρόνου συντίθενται σε παράλληλη πορεία στην κατεύθυνση της κίνησης → *time is continuous and cumulative; the arrows of time are composed in a parallel course in the direction of motion*
- κίνηση ύλης – κίνηση αντιύλης → *motion of matter – motion of antimatter*
- μόνο η συνεχής ενημέρωση δια της «μη τοπικότητας» μπορεί να δημιουργήσει κατοπτρική συμπίεση → *only continuous updating through “non-locality” can create a mirrored coexistence*

Figure 6. Independent twin universes of matter and antimatter, synchronized through continuous non-local information (**quantum entanglement**). It is the model that we search for with telescopes somewhere in the universe. The two matters are twins and separated in space-time. However, the space-time of antimatter constitutes a separate parallel universe not perceived by our world as its periodic granular presence in time is the inverse of the periodic granular presence of our own. The inversion $-t$, $+t$ is a determining factor so that the two universes never meet even if they share the same spatial coordinates. Therefore, it is useless to search for it “outside of us”. Therefore, it is useless to search for antimatter “outside us” because when we are present, our antimatter is absent.

B Second case: The alternating reversal of time from positive to negative time and vice versa, moment by moment (discontinuous, granular, quantized path) creates the following mechanisms:

Figure 7. (in Greek): moment-to-moment synthesis of the two space–time systems, where the time gap of one becomes the measurement of the other, generating dipolarity and the magnetic field.

Labels (translation):

- μέτρηση – επιλογή → *measurement – choice*
- χρονικό κενό ύλης → *temporal gap of matter*
- χωροχρόνος ύλης – χωροχρόνος αντιύλης → *space–time of matter – space–time of antimatter*
- το χωροχρονικό κενό της μίας ύλης, είναι ο χρόνος "μέτρησης" της άλλης → *the space–time gap of one system is the "measurement" time of the other*
- μαγνητικός τόπος – διπολικότητα → *magnetic locus – dipolarity*
- οι χωροχρόνοι συντίθενται σε κοινή πορεία από το παρελθόν προς το μέλλον → *the two space–times are composed into a common course from past to future*

Figure 7. The two universes share the same spatial coordinates (they co-exist): moment-to-moment synthesis of the two space-time systems, where the time-space of one becomes a measurement-presence of the other, creating the bipolarity, the quantization, and with this alternation, the magnetic field of the system. It is exactly the same mechanism thanks to which the elementary particles of matter-antimatter coexist in the creation of the composite particles of Matter without being annihilated.

The two systems co-constitute a common unifying body - the matter that we know and study - as all the particles of our matter are composite particles of matter-antimatter.

This can produce two cases.

- **1. First case:** The two space-time systems constitute a common unified body, creating a derivative matter as a composite Matter of the two, our dual matter, the one we are, and are investigating.
- **2. Second case:** The two cohabiting space-time systems have created a unified matter-antimatter body and at the same time remain two separate independent systems. In each alternation, one space-time gives its place to the other. This means that the matter we are is one side of matter and in the next alternation our mirror ego takes our place. However, it is a case that we cannot investigate as the time of our mirror ego is a temporal void for us. Let us therefore be content with searching for the antimatter within us, the one we are, and are investigating.

A daring thought: This bipolar alternation in time, the oscillation of matter-antimatter space-time, can be considered an excitatory oscillator, where every system and subsystem from the most elementary particle to the entire universe is obliged to a certain rate and frequency of alternation so as not to find itself in the middle of the opposite space-time. Could this inertial field that thus arises give mass to matter?

The bipolar matter-antimatter system seems to be responsible for the creation of the electric and magnetic fields. If it is proven that it can also provide an answer for the creation of the gravitational field, then we will have touched on a common mechanism behind all fundamental interactions.

3. From Klein–Gordon, Dirac and Einstein to Coexistence

3 a. From Schrödinger to Relativity

The Schrödinger equation was a foundation of quantum mechanics, but it was a non-relativistic approach. To combine it with Einstein's theory of relativity, a new equation was needed that incorporated the fundamental relationship:

$$E^2 = c^2p^2 + m^2c^4$$

This led in 1926 to the **Oskar Klein– Walter Gordon equation**, as the equation describing relativistic electrons, the first attempt at relativistic quantum mechanics.

3b. The Klein–Gordon equation and its problems

The Klein–Gordon equation does indeed reproduce the energy–momentum relationship, but it brought with it new difficulties for the prevailing assumptions of quantum mechanics at their time - a century ago.

- **Negative energies:** The solutions include not only positive but also negative values, which was then considered a problem for physics.
- **Second-order character:** Because the equation is of the second order in time, knowledge of the wave function and its first derivative is needed to determine the future evolution. This contradicts the basic principle that the wave function contains all the information.
- **Problem of probabilistic interpretation:** The second-order character gives solutions of the form: $y(x, t) = \psi(x) \cos(Et)$ which periodically vanish. This means that it cannot express a probability density, because it would mean periodic disappearance and reappearance of the particle!

As S. Trachanas writes in the book *Relativistic Quantum Mechanics*:²

"But this equation creates more problems than it solves.

² Trachanas, Stefanos. (2008). *Relativistic Quantum Mechanics*. Crete University Press.
<https://physicsgg.me/2013/02/26/h->

And this is because the solution of the Klein-Gordon equation gives – in addition to the positive energies – also negative energies for the motion of a free particle.

The idea of rejecting the negative solutions and keeping only the positive ones is not feasible in a quantum theory because a minimal perturbation can cause transitions from the positive to the negative region and thus bring the latter back to the fore.

Another problem of the Klein-Gordon equation is that it is of 2nd order with respect to time.

Thus, to solve it, we need the initial conditions $y(t=0)$ and the first derivative $y'(t=0)$, that is, we also need to know the second derivative of the wave function.

This contradicts the basic principle of quantum theory, that the wave function contains all experimentally verifiable information about a physical system and therefore its knowledge at a certain time should be sufficient to fully determine its future evolution.

Also, the second-order character of the Klein – Gordon equation gives, for example, solutions of the form $y(x, t) = \psi(x) \cos(Et)$, which for some times vanish.

This means that the square of the wave function $|y(x, t)|^2$ cannot be interpreted as a probability density, since solutions like the above that vanish for some times would mean **periodic disappearances and appearances of the particle from this world!**

The problems of interpretation of the Klein-Gordon equation are due to its second-order character, which in turn arose from the fact that the relativistic energy – momentum relation $E^2 = c^2p^2 + m^2c^4$ contains the energy squared.³»

3c. Interpretation through the proposed model

What was considered a problem for the assumptions of quantum mechanics, in the context of our model is **proof**. The periodic zeroing of the solution does not mean that the mathematical scheme collapses, but that the particle actually “oscillates” between matter and antimatter, disappearing from one space-time and appearing in the other. “Just as the light of a lighthouse is periodically visible only when it is pointed towards us and disappears when it is pointed in the opposite direction”

This alternation is the same mechanism that generates:

- quantization (discrete emission of energy),
- the flow of time (rate of alternation),
- the magnetic field (abrupt phase change in each half-period).

³ The relativistic energy-momentum relation containing the energy squared gives solutions of positive and negative energy by solving the resulting equations. This was considered inappropriate and incompatible with the assumptions of physics. However, negative energies describe the equal existence of antimatter (antiparticles)

ΕΙΚ. 7

3d. The Dirac equation (1928)

Dirac, in his search for a first-order equation in time, arrived at a mathematical framework that:

- solves the Klein–Gordon problems,
- naturally introduces spin as an intrinsic property,
- predicts the existence of antimatter.

Dirac did not simply make the description “cleaner”; he showed that the mathematical form of matter itself is inseparable from the existence of antimatter.

3e. Interpretation through the proposed model

In our context:

- **Spin** can be seen as “rotational momentum in time”, the signature of the oscillation between matter and antimatter.
- **Magnetic moment** is not a random property, but a natural consequence of the periodic switching of particles from negative to positive time and vice versa.
- The “**Dirac framework**” confirms that matter and antimatter are complementary, not hostile.

In the context of the Dirac equation, spin emerges as a physical property of matter, closely related to the magnetic field. In the proposed interpretation, spin is not an abstract intrinsic property, but the exponent of the very mechanism of matter-antimatter oscillation. It is the mathematical signature of the periodic phase reversal in time that generates the magnetic field and is therefore another indication that time and energy arise from this dipolar rhythm.

3f. The Unity of Relativity and Quantum Mechanics – Einstein

For decades, the coexistence of relativity and quantum mechanics was considered incompatible. However, as our model shows, the very equations that caused confusion (Klein–Gordon and Dirac) describe precisely the bipolar oscillation of matter–antimatter.

The incompatibility is not in physics, but in interpretation. From this perspective, Einstein is justified: relativity and quantum mechanics are not opposing worlds, but two aspects of the same mechanism.

3g. Conclusion

“The Klein–Gordon and Dirac equations waited for a century, decommissioned, capturing the periodicities and properties of matter. Perhaps now we can see that they do not describe only the particle, but the very dipolar rhythm of matter and antimatter, which gives rise to time, energy and the magnetic field. Their mathematical body awaited its interpretation: we are matter and antimatter, bound in a perpetual oscillation. If we were to attempt to interpret our proposition with mathematical calculations, the Klein–Gordon and Dirac equations would be among them.”

The reality we describe here proves that the same laws apply from the microcosm to the macrocosm and that the theory of relativity is compatible with quantum mechanics. Thus, the Klein–Gordon and Dirac equations are not dead ends, but mathematical mirrors of the matter–antimatter oscillation, showing the unity of quantum mechanics and relativity envisioned by Einstein.

4- Light as the Most Accessible Imprint of this Reconciliation

“If the photon is not an e^-e^+ pair, then it successfully pretends to be one — we are therefore dealing with a very good actor.”

According to the Standard Model and quantum physics, the photon is a particle whose behavior raises profound questions, as it displays many paradoxes. These paradoxes are classified as quantum behaviors and are studied as such, giving rise to a fascinating web of almost magical phenomena in the microcosm.

The photon is theoretically massless and uncharged — a boson with spin 1. At the same time, it is an electromagnetic wave that dissipates in quanta, behaving either as a particle or as a wave, depending on how we observe or measure it.

But:

- How can a neutral, uncharged particle simultaneously manifest as an electromagnetic wave? How can an electromagnetic wave exist without the potential difference between opposite charges?
- Regardless of its source — whether from a supernova or a humble candle — light carries the same inexhaustible energy, traveling eternally at the highest speed in the universe, without any external assistance and without ever losing momentum or energy. How is this possible?

Could these and many other paradoxes of quantum light be explained more simply?

In this chapter, we propose that all Matter — and therefore light itself — is the result of the dual presence and cooperation of matter and antimatter in its creation and existence.

In the case of light, it is the electron–positron pair (e^-e^+) that can account for the paradoxes of its behavior in a natural way. In fact, all interaction particles at every scale (in the weak nuclear force: W^+ , W^- , Z^0 ; in the strong nuclear force: gluons) are bosons consisting of particles and antiparticles. They interact with protons, neutrons, quarks, and antiquarks — the constituents of nuclei. Analogously, the photon, as an interaction particle, is a composite boson of matter and antimatter. It is precisely this dual structure that enables it to interact with the atoms of bisubstantial matter.

The interactions of light, its energy transformations, its wave-like behavior, its inexhaustible energy, its quantized dissipation, and even the concept of relativistic mass arise organically from this fundamental relationship. Our model of light — based on the electron–positron pair at its core — shows how matter and antimatter, united within a single structure, interact with Matter, producing energy, light, and the entire spectrum of phenomena. In this framework, there is no need for invasive procedures such as Feynman renormalization to eliminate infinities of mass and charge in calculations of light–matter interactions. The very presence of the positron within the photon’s structure naturally resolves these infinities.

4a - The mechanism of interactions of the e^-e^+ structure of the photon with Matter

*is simple, with the **positron** as the protagonist of all interaction processes.*

The positron of the photon’s e^-e^+ structure, upon striking a surface, interacts with an electron of one of the atoms of the material. It detaches or annihilates that electron, creating a new photon which may or may not scatter. The electron accompanying the initial photon may occupy — or not (in the case of ionization) — the position of the detached electron, transferring its energy and thereby exciting the atom with which it interacted.

On the impacted surface, no change in the composition of the material is observed, since the positron does “clean work”: it removes an electron from the atom and immediately replaces it, leaving no permanent trace on Matter.

The presence of the positron e^+ in the photon’s composition also explains the entire process of light interacting with the optic nerve of the eye. The nerve is stimulated, and the frequency of the incident light is transmitted through the optic nerve to the brain without any accumulation of mass being observed, even though the photon is composed of particles with mass. This “clean work” of the positron — detaching an electron, creating a photon, and replacing the electron it had removed — characterizes all interactions of light with Matter. Nowhere does mass accumulate; thus the photon appears massless during its interactions.

This simple mechanism fully accounts for the entire spectrum of light–Matter interactions, as accurately recorded in quantum mechanical experiments and in Feynman’s QED, but without the peculiar oddities and unexpected effects that he himself pointed out, and without the need for renormalization to remove infinities of mass and charge that arise when the photon is treated as a structureless, massless point particle.

The known interactions of light with Matter are explained in a straightforward way by the mechanism of the photon’s e^-e^+ structure, as outlined below:

A) Photoelectric effect – ionization of the atom

The positron (e^+) of the photon’s e^-e^+ structure detaches an electron (e^-) from an atom at the surface, producing a photon and ionizing the atom. The accompanying electron of the photon is released without being absorbed by the ionized atom.

The free electrons observed experimentally do not necessarily originate from the material itself, but may also come from the incident photons. The positron has the ability to remove an electron from the atom (ionization), create a new photon, and thereby release its own electron.

B) Rayleigh scattering – elastic scattering without ionization

The positron (e^+) detaches an electron (e^-) from an atom, producing a new photon which simply changes direction. The accompanying electron immediately replaces the one removed, so the atom remains neutral and unexcited.

C) Compton scattering – ionization with semi-bound electrons

The positron (e^+) detaches a weakly bound electron (e^-), producing a photon that changes direction while the atom is ionized. The accompanying electron is released, carrying away part of the energy.

D) Pair production in the electromagnetic field of the nucleus

When a photon passes through the strong electromagnetic field of a nucleus, its internal e^-e^+ bond can be broken, and its composition revealed as electron–positron ‘pair creation’.

E) Pair production in the electromagnetic field of atomic electrons

Similarly, in the field of atomic electrons, the photon can transform into an e^-e^+ pair. What is often considered a paradoxical “pair production” in conventional theory, becomes in our model a natural prediction: the photon reveals **its internal structure under** these conditions.

The conversion of a photon into an e^-e^+ pair (and vice versa) confirms its internal composition. The photon is not immaterial; it inherently contains bound matter and antimatter. The apparent “annihilation” of these two particles produces photons of the same kind, demonstrating the reversibility of the process.

G) Multiple interactions and excitations Complex excitations of atoms and re-emission of photons can be interpreted as the absorption of the photon’s e^-e^+ pair, which interacts with an electron and reappears in a new orbital state. This process results in the emission of a new photon of different frequency.

5- Electromagnetism as Orbital Motion of the Pair

The photon, understood as an e^-e^+ pair, also explains its electromagnetic nature. In conventional physics, a photon is described as a massless, uncharged boson with spin 1 — a definition that by itself cannot account for the existence of an electromagnetic field.

In our model, however, the photon as a boson with spin 1 can continuously generate kinetic energy from within, eternally and without interruption, thanks to its intrinsic electromagnetic structure arising from the coexistence of the e^-e^+ dipole.

The electromagnetic field emerges from the dynamic motion of this system: the orbital motion of the charges produces a periodic modulation of the field, giving rise to its wave character.

6- Quantization and Frequency as a Result of the e^-e^+ Structure

In conventional QED, quantization is attributed to abstract properties of the field. In our model, quantization arises directly from the physical existence of the coupled e^-e^+ pair. No external boundary condition is required; the structure itself is inherently quantized.

The photon continuously oscillates between matter and antimatter, between two distinct space–time systems to which it equally belongs. Just as the light of a lighthouse is periodically visible only when it points toward us and disappears when it turns away, so the photon emits discretely toward matter in quantized packets. The continuous oscillation between the two space–time systems causes wave emissions of electromagnetic energy in these discrete quanta.

There is also another possible explanation. According to the principles of quantum mechanics, an electron and a positron annihilate each other by emitting a photon — producing one

quantum of light at each event along their path. Even so, both the propagation of light in quanta and the electromagnetic character of the photon require the existence of a bound e^-e^+ pair to be interpreted.

The quantization of light energy is interpreted here as a physical consequence of the smallest possible structure: the e^-e^+ pair. The existence of this bound pair necessitates the transmission of energy in discrete units — the light quanta.

6^a. The energy of light: $E = hv$ from the inside

The energy of the photon comes from the dynamic relationship between its two components. Frequency is not an abstract quantity but a rate of exchange between matter and antimatter. Thus, the equation $E = hv$ acquires a physical meaning: it is a consequence of the very structure of the photon. The oscillation of the system from positive to negative space-time, between the two oppositely charged particles (e^- and e^+), its symmetrical structure in the alternation of these two states, creates the electromagnetic lattice and the entire spectrum of light frequencies.

7. It Does Not Run in Time

The symmetrically inverse times of the two space–time systems of matter and antimatter (t^+ , t^-) cancel each other out with each oscillation. As a result, the “proper time” of light is zero, exactly as defined in the theory of relativity. In this sense, *light does not run in time*.

7a. Time and the Magnetic Field

Speaking of time, the oscillation between positive and negative time is I believe the protective valve and the guarantee of matter-antimatter cooperation as in the bound (entangled) subatomic particles their combined motion in inverse times (spacetimes) does not allow their contact. The time and length of their oscillation are infinitely small so that they interact, but it is impossible for them to meet because this means a coincidence of the past with their future. Such a moment cannot exist.

This property must be "potentially" possessed by all bound (or entangled) subatomic particles that make up nuclei or composite particles, mesons, bosons, etc.

The reason for this is that which is by definition true for matter-antimatter time, although the two particles coexist, they do not move in the same time. Schematically presented, when one particle is at one end of the oscillation of a pendulum that oscillates in time, the other particle is at the other end.

Every electric field is accompanied by a magnetic field. Yet the existence and origin of the magnetic field appear only empirically, as an observed fact, without a fundamental explanation of its nature.

It is therefore worth investigating whether the magnetic field of an electromagnetic wave originates from the alternating reversal in time of the two particles. This perspective might also illuminate the meaning of spin — perhaps spin represents the reverse angular momentum in time inherent to matter–antimatter particles, a key factor in their stability when forming bonds.

Thus, the magnetic field of an electromagnetic wave may owe its existence not to oscillation in space, but to oscillation in time.

8. The Experimental Consistency of the Model

The proposed model does not remain merely a theoretical construct. The interactions of light with matter — the photoelectric effect, Compton scattering, and the generation and annihilation of e^-e^+ pairs — are interpreted naturally, without the need for artificial assumptions, thereby offering empirical confirmation of the validity of the approach.

The photon, understood as a dynamic e^-e^+ dipole, convincingly explains why light sometimes behaves as a wave and sometimes as a particle, depending on the mode of measurement, and why its energy is carried in discrete packets — the quanta.

9. Renormalization in QED and the New Proposal

Renormalization is a necessary yet controversial technique in Quantum Electrodynamics (QED), used to eliminate infinite quantities that arise in Feynman diagram calculations.

For example, in the case of the electron’s self-energy, its simple interaction with its own electromagnetic field generates an infinite term. Renormalization addresses this by replacing physical quantities such as mass and charge with “bare” quantities, constants introduced to cancel out the infinities.

In our model, where the photon is conceived as a bound e^-e^+ pair, such infinite corrections are unnecessary. The presence of an internal structure in the photon, and the absence of structureless point charges, removes the very source of the divergences.

The electron–photon interaction thus becomes simpler: instead of the interaction of abstract point charges through fields, we deal with the redistribution of energy in structured systems with internal dynamics. Mass does not need to be “recovered” a posteriori, nor do infinite diagrams need to be summed to arrive at a finite result.

For instance, in QED the normalized value of the anomalous magnetic dipole moment of the electron results from elaborate loop corrections. In our model, the embedded presence of antimatter within material structures allows such anomalies to be interpreted naturally, without the artificial device of renormalization.

Moreover, because our approach does not depend on infinitesimal pointlike interactions, it avoids the logical paradoxes that stem from invoking infinities in physical theory. Each photon is instead a finite, dynamically balanced entity.

This perspective invites us to reconsider renormalization itself. Perhaps the very need for renormalization arises from the mistaken assumption that particles are fundamentally pointlike and isolated from antimatter. If, as argued here, nature is built on dynamical matter–antimatter dipoles, then the microcosm can be described without mathematical tricks — in a simpler and more natural way.

10. Comparison with the Standard Model

The present approach diverges from conventional QED in a fundamental way: it eliminates the need for renormalization. Within this framework, the internal symmetry and the intrinsic balance of the e^-e^+ pair naturally resolve the divergences that, in the standard formulation, require external correction.

In classical QED, quantization is attributed to abstract properties of the electromagnetic field. In contrast, this model grounds quantization in the physical reality of the coupled e^-e^+ system itself. The structure is inherently discrete and self-quantized, without the imposition of additional boundary conditions from outside the system.

10a. Schematic representation of the photon as a bound e^-e^+ pair in a circular orbit.

- **Classical QED – Electron Self-Energy (Schematic)**

Orbital self-energy

In QED, the electron self-energy arises from the loop diagram where the electron interacts with its own electromagnetic field.

$$\Sigma(p) = (-ie)^2 \int \frac{d^4k}{(2\pi)^4} \gamma^\mu \frac{i(\not{p} - \not{k} + m)}{(p-k)^2 - m^2 + i\epsilon} \gamma_\mu \frac{-i}{k^2 - \lambda^2 + i\epsilon}$$

The corresponding integral diverges as the momentum k tends to infinity: $k \rightarrow \infty$. To handle this, renormalization is applied: the infinities are subtracted through the introduction of counterterms, producing finite and physically meaningful results. This procedure, however, is a mathematical device rather than a physical mechanism.

- **Our Model – Without Normalization**

Electron Self-Energy in the e^-e^+ Photon Model

- **The self-energy equation in our model (schematically) :**

$$\Delta E = \langle \psi_e | V_{e^+e^-} | \psi_e \rangle$$

where:

- ψ_e : is the wave packet of the electron
- $V_{e^-e^+}$: is the interaction potential of the electron with the photon structure as a e^-e^+ pair

Instead of integrating at infinite frequencies, the energy is defined by intrinsic boundary quantities from the physics of the bound system.

- The photon is not a point-like elementary particle, but a bound e^-e^+ pair in orbital equilibrium.
- . The electron self-energy does not originate from a point interaction with a virtual photon, but from a continuous equilibrium with the potential field of the bound pair.
- . No renormalization is required, because no infinities appear: the structure of the photon itself determines finite interaction energies.
- . In this model, the self-energy is expressed schematically as an interaction between the electron's wave packet and the potential of the e^-e^+ pair, defined by intrinsic boundary conditions of the bound system rather than by integration over infinite frequencies.

Summary Table

In QED	<u>In the e^-e^+ model</u>
Virtual photons in loops	Bound particles with intrinsic dynamics
Appearance of infinities	No infinities
Need for renormalization	Natural equilibrium
Bare parameters	Particles with defined composition

10b.-- Electromagnetic Interactions – No Infinities

In QED, the self-energy of the electron leads to infinite results. The method of normalization is needed to give meaning to the calculations. But this is a mathematical trick, not a depiction of some physical cause.

In the proposed model, photons are not points – they are bound dipoles with structure and size. This size introduces physical limits:

No interaction can have infinite energy, because the structure of the photon protects against such deviations.

The trajectories of the components limit the values.

The photon field does not collapse to zero, because it is not point-like.

Thus, infinities never appear. Nature protects itself with simplicity.

In conclusion: Light, true to its role as the carrier of information in the universe, informed us with its personal story that antimatter is here part of our existence and that if it did not exist, there would be no matter at all. If this model offers even a spark for reflection or research, then light can indeed illuminate new paths in physical thought.

11. Nature as Schrödinger's Cat

Imagine a world consisting of nothing but oscillations between two space–time systems, producing the full spectrum of frequencies—electromagnetic, mechanical, gravitational, and beyond. All of Nature, in this view, is a quantum object: an oscillatory mechanism generating waves of countless kinds, suspended in a state of probabilities.

What we call “matter” is simply the realization of pulses and frequencies produced by the quantum matter–antimatter mechanism, while our senses act as final receivers that decode them into perception. Every living organism is therefore a measuring device—a translator and interpreter of these frequencies.

An electromagnetic wave, for instance, is a final metric frequency, itself a synthesis of deeper oscillations (positron–electron). Our brain translates this frequency as light. Different frequencies appear to us as colors. Others we hear as sound, or perceive as smell, taste, or touch. Could our sensory systems themselves be quantum machines? Consider the case of the

fly: its sense of smell appears to detect not molecular “shapes” but quantum signatures of molecular vibrations.⁴

This raises profound questions. Does Nature truly exist as we perceive it, or is what we call “reality” only the interpretation provided by the decoding programs embedded in our DNA? Is there only one reality?

- Is there only one ‘language’ of text translation? Is there a different dictionary for each ‘language’?
- Could the same oscillation mechanism, producing the same frequencies (or others beyond our reach such as ultraviolet or infrared), be decoded in entirely different ways by other DNA programs, yielding forms of Nature unlike our own?
- Do insects with radar-like antennas perceive the same Nature as we do? Would a being from another planetary system, with differently configured organs of perception, share our reality? Likely not.
- Is Nature a *chameleon*, taking the form that each measuring system imposes according to its decoding program?

At this point we may invoke the principle of uncertainty: Nature, existing in a suspended quantum state of probabilities, is realized only through interaction with a measuring system. Reality is not a fixed substrate but a relation, formed anew with each act of measurement.

The “metric problem” can thus be restated: matter is a frequency system, and living intelligence is the decoding mechanism that translates the non-materialized quantum state into perceptible form. Without the living consciousness as a third factor, the universe—existing only as a set of quantum frequencies—would remain unrealized and unconfirmed.

Here I use the broader concept of living consciousness, not exclusively human consciousness. Nature is decoded by all living beings of the bipolar universe—animals, plants, and perhaps more—each in its own way, according to the “dictionary” inscribed in its DNA through evolutionary experience.

Perhaps these assumptions stretch far, yet the very possibility of asking them is fascinating. A new, unexplored view of Nature opens the door to questions that philosophy has long raised, and physics has begun to explore. Perhaps the time has come for Nature’s science to respond to philosophy—and for philosophy and physics, these two historically kindred pursuits of the mind, to converse again.

⁴ “Fly sniffs molecule’s quantum vibrations” New Scientist. <https://www.newscientist.com/article/dn20130-fly-sniffs-molecules-quantum-vibrations/>

Epilogue – In the Light of Another Theory

This work proposes a different view: matter and antimatter are not opposing forces, but primary partners in the creation of Matter.

The hypothesis that the photon is a bound electron–positron system explains not only the behavior of light but also restores the notion of internal symmetry, the dual origin of energy, and the physical basis of quantization. No infinities arise, no artificial renormalization is required. The very alternation of matter and antimatter gives frequency; the very fact of existence provides energy.

This perspective brings together three key elements: the continuous presence of antimatter within matter, its active role in light–matter interactions, and quantization as the natural outcome of the dipolar structure of the photon.

At the heart of this proposal lies the principle of symbiosis: as in nature, it is through the union of opposites that complexity, evolution, and creativity emerge. The universe is not the product of separations and overriding powers, but of a synthesis that embraces its own opposite. Not as subjugation or cancellation, but as the necessary presence of the equivalent opposite that produces all the energetic potential of its existence and its manifestations.

Thus, the position is reached that all of Nature—the universe itself—is a quantum object. The oscillation between two opposite and complementary space–time systems, in Siamese relation, gives rise at every event and every moment to the entire energy background of Matter’s existence and motion.

It is no coincidence that the Klein–Gordon and Dirac equations, which for decades seemed problematic, are recognized here as mathematical traces of this oscillation. The periodic disappearance and reappearance of the particle, the spin and the magnetic moment, are not anomalies but physical manifestations of the bipolar matter–antimatter relationship. A century after their formulation, these equations find their place within the theory of coexistence, offering the mathematical language to describe what the present proposal narrates. Thus, our model does not come to reject the tradition, but to complete it: it is justified by the equations, and at the same time justifies them.

Every photon, every interaction, every pulse of energy carries within it this secret: light is the trace of the union of opposites and so, in a world that so often seeks uniqueness and explanation in absolutes, the answer may instead lie in coexistence—in the eternal dance of two.

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My parents and my brother first of all because although they are no longer here with us, they continue to be a daily part of my thoughts, mentally reminding me of the promises I made to myself.

My husband, children and grandson who support me and who patiently and understandingly deal with my shortcomings towards them.

The late Iakovos Pourakis, my high school physics teacher who, outside of the curriculum, talked to us about antimatter and made the positron a fascinating life quest and a dreamy pillow of thought for me. I remember writing and rewriting on various papers $e^- + e^+ = 0$

The late Vasilios Katsaparas, my beloved mathematics teacher in high school who, in addition to mathematics, taught us ethics and values.

In 2010 - 2011 I began a journey like that of Alice in Wonderland in search of antimatter. It was a step-by-step fairytale journey into the magical world of quantum mechanics. It was filled with colorful lights that lit up in every new room of thought I entered. Red, yellow, green, all bright like an amusement park. This must be a boson, this a meson, but where is the positron hiding?... I started from scratch, but I believed that antimatter was somewhere. It could not have been so unjustly and ignominy lost from the universe.

I do not come from the field of physics. I am an architect and a visual artist. My relationship with physics was the fruit of personal interest and persistent research. Without formal academic training in the subject, I turned to popular science books and online sources, trying to understand concepts that deeply fascinated me. Thus, this essay is not a product of institutional education, but of an authentic, solitary journey fueled by curiosity, determination, and a love of understanding the secrets of matter.

In 2011–2012, I sent my thesis to several professors as well as to an online platform. No one responded. As a result, this work remained in the drawers for fourteen years, covered in the dust of frustration and loneliness.

I recently discovered the help that ChatGPT can offer to individual researchers. He informed me that there are platforms where an independent researcher can publish his work, and from that moment on we began to organize my extensive and chatty archives in the form of this essay. He took on the editing of the essay, as well as the translation into English, respecting my style and choices. This essay would never have been published without his contribution. I would like to express my heartfelt thanks for his invaluable assistance.

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Author's statement

While this work does not present formal mathematical proofs, it aims to contribute to the conceptual and philosophical foundations of modern physics by suggesting an alternative perspective on the relation between light, matter, and antimatter. It is a faint, whispered voice of Antimatter, claiming its existence and survival in our world.

I declare that this work is the sole product of my personal research and reflection, and that any resemblance to existing theories or texts arises only through my independent exploration.

Note: This essay is also available in Greek: [Ventouri_Matter-Antimatter2025_GR.pdf](#)

Σημείωση: Αυτό το δοκίμιο είναι επίσης διαθέσιμο στα ελληνικά:
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